

Scaling Approach to Finding the Maxwell-Boltzmann Distribution and Maximization

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Jan. 22, 2026

In a previous note, we suggested that one may obtain the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution through a scaling approach which does not use reaction balance or maximization of entropy. In other words, it does not appear at first glance to use any extremization idea. We will show here that this approach works in any dimension for the nonrelativistic case. The question then becomes: Why should a scaling approach select a maximum entropy or reaction balance result (which is based on a uniform distribution of product $p(e_i)p(e_j)$ probabilities). How is it that an extremum result appears if no a priori extremization is employed.

We argue that in fact a maximization strategy is applied in the scaling approach because one sets the coefficient of dT to 0 (instead of considering all powers of dT) and only considers $p \rightarrow p+dp/dT dT$. In general it is the sum of the full series which arises when $T \rightarrow T+dT$ which is 0, not the first coefficient. We argue that setting the first coefficient to 0 is equivalent to choosing an extremum, i.e. one which does not change a function to first order when one changes the variable in question, here $p(e_i/T)$ probability to first order.

We note that the scaling approach is based on the following idea.

$$E = T \left\{ \int de e^{\text{power } b} c_1^{-1} p(e_i/T) \right\} / \left\{ \int de e^{\text{power } b} c_1^{-1} p(e_i/T) \right\} \quad ((1))$$

Here $b = .5$ for three dimensions and $p(e_i/T)$ is unnormalized. In general, the factor of T is a fixed number. If one changes $T \rightarrow T+dT$ then the sum of all powers of dT in an expansion should add to zero. It is a special case if the first order term is 0. We show that this special case is the MB distribution in the nonrelativistic case for any power b . By forcing the Number in $E = T$ Number to remain unchanged by changing $p(e_i/T) \rightarrow p+dp/dT dT$, one is choosing an extremum solution. (It is not clear, however, that this approach works in the relativistic case because one does not have $e^{\text{power } b}$, while reaction balance or maximization of entropy subject to constraints still does.)

Showing that The Scaling Approach Yields the Maxwell-Boltzmann Solution for All Dimensions in the Nonrelativistic Case

We have used the scaling approach in (1) for three dimensions, but here we wish to show that it holds for any measure of the form:

$$pp dp^{4*3.14} = e^{\text{power } b} c_1^{-1} de \quad ((2)) \quad \text{Here } p \text{ is momentum and } c_1 \text{ is a constant linked to } 4*3.14 \text{ etc.}$$

((2)) holds for all dimensions in the nonrelativistic case, but not for the relativistic one.

We first change $T \rightarrow T+dT$ and consider a first order change in p due to dT . We then argue that one wishes to have the coefficient of dT equal 0. (This will be discussed in further detail in another section.)

Setting $y=e^{i/T}$ $dp/dt = -y/T dp/dy$ ((3)) and $E= T * \text{Number}$

The first order in dT correction to Number is:

$$\text{Number } dp/y -yp - yy dp/dy \quad ((4))$$

((4)) is contained in the integral $\int de e^{\text{power } b}$ and this integral should be 0. We do not set ((4)) itself to 0, but the integral to find a solution for $p(y)$.

We choose $p(y) = \exp(-y)$ as a test.

We note that $A= 1/N_1 \int y \exp(-y) y^{\text{power } b} dy = \text{Number}/T$ ((5)) (we consider $T=1$ for convenience)

Here N_1 is the normalization of $p(e^{i/T})$ at T . Note $p(e^{i/T})$ is unnormalized, but $E=\text{Number}*T$ must include normalization.

One may integrate by parts so that $A = - (b+1) \text{Number}$ ((6))

The term $-yydp/dy$ becomes $yy \exp(-y)$ and integration by parts yields:

$$(2+b) \text{Number} = (1+\text{Number}) \text{Number} \quad ((7))$$

This may be compared with $-\text{Number}(1+\text{Number})$ from the terms $\text{Number} (y dp/dy) - py$.

Thus, one obtains 0 for the integral of ((4)) for any dimension for the nonrelativistic case, i.e. any $e^{\text{power } b}$ de integral over phase space. Unfortunately the relativistic case is not of this form and so we restrict the scaling approach to the nonrelativistic case.

The Notion of Extremization in the Scaling Approach

The maximization of Shannon's entropy subject to constraints clearly selects an extremum solution. Reaction balance, which is equivalent to:

$$p(e_i)p(e_j) = p(e_k)p(e_l) \text{ for } e_i+e_j = e_k+e_l \quad ((8))$$

considers a uniform distribution for $p(e_i)p(e_j)$ if $e_i+e_j=E_1$. This is a least information solution.

Both of these approaches select a special extremum type solution. The question we ask is: Does the scaling approach also select an extremum solution? A priori, there was no mention of maximizing anything or minimizing information. We suggest that it is the condition that:

$$\text{The coefficient of } dT = 0 \text{ together with } p \rightarrow p+dp/dT dT \quad ((9))$$

is an extremum condition. In general, one does not have to force the coefficient of dT to be 0. One simply has the full power law expansion in all powers of dT be 0 and considers $p(T+dT)$ not only the first order term.

In particular, consider any unnormalized possible probability function $p_1(e_i/T)$. $p_1(e_i/T)$ is not the Maxwell-Boltzmann result $\exp(-e_i/T)$. Then:

$$E_{ave} = \left\{ \int e^b p_1(e_i/T) \right\} / \left\{ \int e^b p_1(e_i/T) \right\} \quad ((10))$$

Scaling holds in general for any $p_1(e_i/T)$, i.e one may use $y=e_i/T$ and an extra T is pulled out of the numerator. Thus:

$$E_{ave} = \text{Number1} * T \quad ((11))$$

holds for any $p_1(e_i/T)$ unnormalized probability distribution, not just the Maxwell-Boltzmann one which maximizes Shannon's entropy subject to constraints or satisfies reaction balance.

In such a case, if $T \rightarrow T+dT$, then Number1 must remain unchanged, but in general one must consider all powers in the expansion of $p(e_i/(T+dT))$. One cannot simply consider the first order change in $dp(e_i)$ and the first order change in the integrals.

To do so, as we did in the section above is to choose a special solution, i.e one for which a first order change in $p(e_i/T)$ does not change a function (namely Number for $E = \text{Number} * T$) to first order, i.e. the coefficient of $dT=0$. Setting the coefficient of dT to 0 means selecting a special extremum solution and we argue that this is why the scaling approach in the nonrelativistic case matches the results of more formal maximization processes such as maximization of Shannon's entropy or reaction balance.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we considered a scaling approach in (1) which yields the Maxwell-Boltzmann solution. This approach may be also applied to the Tsallis distribution using $E = \sum_i p_i(e_i/T)^q$. The approach does not use any a priori notion of maximization as is used in maximization of Shannon's entropy or reaction balance. The idea is to write:

$$E = \left\{ \int e^b p(e_i/T) \right\} / \left\{ \int e^b p(e_i/T) \right\} = \text{Number} * T$$

Here $p(e_i/T)$ is not normalized and the above applies to any dimension for the nonrelativistic case. Unfortunately, that does not include the relativistic situation. The idea is then to change $T \rightarrow T+dT$ and consider $p \rightarrow p + dp/dT dT$ such that the coefficient of dT is 0. This yields a unique solution, namely the Maxwell-Boltzmann one.

We argue in this note that the expression for E above holds for any $p(e_i/T)$ (extremum or not), but that Number remains unchanged if one considers changes due to all orders dT , not simply a first order change and a coefficient of 0 for dT . Thus, by considering only $p - p + dp/dT dT$ and

and only the coefficient of dT (as being 0), we argue that we are choosing an extremum solution. This is why one obtains the Maxwell-Boltzmann solution, we suggest.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Speculation on Information, Scaling and the Maxwell-Boltzmann and Tsallis Distributions (preprint, zenodo, 2026)